

Supplemental Table S1

Clinical data of pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma cases.

Case No.	Sex	Age (years)	Tumor size	TNM stage	Differentiation	Lymphovascular invasion	Perineural invasion
1628870*	Female	60	1.7 cm	T1N1M0	Moderate	Yes	Yes
4385250*	Male	48	3.4 cm	T2N1M0	Moderate	Yes	Yes
4442070*	Male	55	3.8 cm	T2N0M0	Moderate	Yes	No
1058667	Male	77	1.5 cm	T1N0M0	Moderate	Yes	No
2305093*	Female	64	2.4 cm	T2N0M0	Well	No	No
6368006*	Female	58	2.5 cm	T2N0M0	Moderate	No	No
6823275	Female	77	2.5 cm	T2N2M0	Moderate	Yes	Yes
6514657*	Female	64	6.0 cm	T3N1M0	Moderate	Yes	No
6976133	Male	74	6.0 cm	T3N0M0	Well	Yes	No
6811475*	Female	77	2.5 cm	T2N0M0	Moderate	Yes	No

Asterisk indicates the case detected with islet aggregation in resection margin.